

PERCEIVED IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 12 SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Perceived Impact of Social Media on the Academic Performance of Grade 12 Senior High School Students

Rolan B. Lactawan, * Santiago E. Sidro Jr., Aris A. Lapada
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study determines the perceived impact of social media on the academic performance of grade 12 students of Hilabaan National High School, Dolores I District, Division of Eastern Samar. This study employed a descriptive correlation design to examine and describe relationships between student profiles, their usage of social media, and the impact of social media on their academic performance. The respondents that were chosen in this study was taken out from two different class sections, a total of 45 learners which were 33 HUUMSS, and 12 TVL tracks. They were considered to have experience access and usage of social media networking sites. The results have founded out an increase in social media usage that is associated with a decline in students' academic performance. Furthermore, the less frequent usage of social media may lead to a better chance of good academic performance of the students. This suggests for further exploration of some other factors that may affect the academic performance of the students in relation to social media usage.

Keywords: *academic performance, social media*

Introduction

We are living in an era dominated by online correspondence where the power of the cyberspace influences nearly every aspect of our lives many people have become “technoholics” individuals who are so obsessed with technology that they cannot imagine life without their gadgets such as smartphones laptops and tablets. We are using these gadgets to connect and interact with our family, friends’, relatives’, co-workers and etc. Any web site encouraging social interaction is considered as social media. As of January 2020, the Philippines had one of the highest social media usage rates in southeast Asia with about 67 percent of the population using social networks on average Filipinos spent nearly four hours per day on social media according to Sanchez (2020).

Recently the rise of social media platforms has notably influence different aspects of daily life including education for grade 12 senior high school student’s social media can be both beneficial and detrimental to their academic performance platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and TikTok have become central to the lives of adolescents providing opportunities for better communication collaboration and access to educational resources (Jones et al., 2021).

However, the extensive use of social media also brings concerns about potential negative effects on students’ academic performance for example excessive social media use may lead to diminished concentration procrastination and decreased engagement with academic activities as stated by Smith and Anderson (2020).

The integration of social media into everyday life has significantly altered the dynamics of communication and education. Social media’s potential as an educational resource cannot be overstated. Platforms such as YouTube and Khan Academy provide students with access content, enabling them to supplement their classroom learning with tutorials and instructional videos (Habes & Salloum, 2020). Moreover, social media promotes collaborative learning environments by allowing students to create virtual study groups, share resources, and participate in academic discussions (Thompson & Kelly, 2020). This peer-to-peer interaction can enhance understanding and retention of complex subjects, contributing positively to academic performance (Torres & Gonzales, 2021)

Recent studies have highlighted the benefits of social media for educational purposes. For instance, Al-Marouf et al. (2021) founded out that during the covid-19 pandemic, platforms like Google Meet facilitated continuity in education, helping students adapt to remote learning environment. Similarly, Campbell and Wang (2021) reported that social media could reduce feelings of isolation and maintain student’s engagement during periods of school closure.

Research by Thompson and Loughheed (2022) highlights a dual role of social media in education. On one hand, it can facilitate peer support and provide a platform for sharing academic materials. On the other hand, it can also serve as a significant distraction, leading to time mismanagement and lower academic outcomes. The association between social media usage and students’ academic outcomes is multifaceted, requiring a thorough exploration of the specific contexts and patterns of the utilization of social media among students (Brown & Johnson, 2023).

Despite its educational benefits, excessive social media usage can adversely influence academic performance. According to Nguyen and Nguyen (2023) found that high engagement with social media is associated with academic distractions, procrastination, and reduced time for studying. The addictive nature of social media, driven by features such as constant notifications and the fear of missing out (FOMO), can significantly interfere with students’ concentration and focus on their academic tasks (Lim & Lee, 2023). High engagement with social media has associated with reduced attention spans, sleep deprivation, and increased anxiety, all of which negatively impact academic performance (Nguyen & Nguyen, (2023).

In addition, in the study of Raman and Khan (2023) observed that excessive social media use leads to sleep deprivation, which adversely affects students' cognitive functions and academic performance. This is consistent with findings by Andrews and Arnorld (2023), who reported the digital distractions from social media result in lower academic achievement among high school students.

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly impacted the role of social media in education. According to Williams and Patel (2021), the transition to online learning during the pandemic led to a greater reliance on social media for academic purposes. While this shift supported continued learning, it also blurred the lines between study and leisure time, which could potentially affect academic performance. The pandemic has heightened the significance of social media in education, making it a crucial tool for communication and collaboration between students and teachers. However, this increased dependence on digital platforms has also highlighted potential drawbacks, such as negative effects on academic performance due to more screen time and fewer face-to-face interactions (Garcia et al., 2021).

The Covid-19 pandemic has amplified the complexities of social media use among students. The shift to online learning increased students' reliance on digital platforms, including social media, for educational purposes (Chen & Yan, 2023). However, this reliance also blurred the lines between academic and recreational use of social media, making it challenging for students to manage their time effectively (Johnson & Wilson, 2023). This increased screen time and digital engagement potentially exacerbated the negative impacts of social media on academic performance (Campbell & Wang, 2021).

The impact of social media on the academic outcome varies by region and culture. In Vietnam, Pham and Huynh (2022) observed that social media use among high school students had both good and bad influence on academics, relating on the content received and the level of parental supervision. In South Korea, Kim and Choi (2021) found that peer interactions on social media had a significant effect on academic outcome, underscoring the role of social networks in shaping students' academic behaviors. Conversely, El-Badawy and Hashem (2021) reported that in Egypt, excessive social media use led to marked declines in academic performance, highlighting the negative impacts of unregulated social media engagement.

With these various observations from different academic settings, this study was decided to be tackled by the researchers. This is prompted due to the result of the quarter four School Monitoring, Evaluation and Adjustment (SMEA) report for academic year 2022-2023. It was seen that Hilabaan NHS senior high school learners scores above par with the national standard passing score of 75%. During the first quarter mean percentile score of 12th Grade Senior High School learners is at 89.74% across learning areas with introduction to philosophy of the human person with the highest MPS of 93.43% and discipline ideas in social science with lowest MPS of 82.00%. These learners are with daily access to social media platforms and other computer-based technologies (SMEA, DepEd Hilabaan NHS, 2023).

School officials, teachers and the district SMEA team are in demands of a more evidence-based characterization of the previewed positive or negative influence of social media usage in the learning activities and learning outcomes of students prompted this researcher to delve into this study (SMEA, 2023). It is therefore essential to establish a research-based data set to support the claim that social media impacts how learners think and learn. This data is crucial for educators and teachers in developing innovative lessons and effective curriculum delivery. Consequently, the researcher sought to establish the perceived effectiveness of social networking sites on the academic outcome of senior high school students.

Research Questions

This research determined the perceived impact of social media usage to the academic performance of Grade 12 learners of Hilabaan National High School, Dolores I District, Division of Eastern Samar under the standard and competency-based curriculum of the K to 12 programs of the Department of Education. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the affiliation and frequency of exposure to social media of grade 12 students of Hilabaan NHS in terms of: a) type of social media network sites b) frequency of use and access c) purpose of use and access d) frequency of content engagement
2. What is the grade point mean percentile scores (MPS) of grade 12 students of Hilabaan NHS across all learning areas?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the affiliation and frequency of exposure to social media usage and academic performance of Grade 12 students in Hilabaan NHS?

Methodology

Research Design

To address the issues outlined in this study, the researcher used a descriptive correlation design to examine and identify correlations between the student's social media usage, and its influence on academic performance. As defined by McCombes (2023) a descriptive research design is a systematic approach to describe a population or a phenomenon. In this design, the researchers do not control or manipulate the variables but only tries to observe and measure it.

While, the correlational research design according to the definition of Bhandari (2023) stating that this design tries to make inquiries about the relationship between variables without any manipulation or control over it.

Respondents

Since the number of identified respondents was relatively small, the researchers decided to use a total enumeration sampling, including all Grade 12 senior high school students currently enrolled at Hilabaan National High School. The inclusion criterion was that participants must have access to and use social media networking sites. The respondents for this study are twelfth grade senior high school learners from Hilabaan National High School for the 2023-2024 academic year. A total of 45 students were selected, comprising 33 from the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUUMSS) track and 12 from the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) track, all of whom have experience with social media networking sites during the academic year.

Instrument

This study utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire to gather data on the effects of social media and networking sites to the students' academic outcomes. The questionnaire was designed to address specific research objectives and included several sections. The first section focuses on the collection of data on students' exposure to social media, examining the level of involvement, frequency of use, and time spent on these platforms to determine the perceived impact of such. The second part assessed the academic performance of the participants by requesting information about their Grade Point Average (GPA) for the first semester of the 2023-2024 school year. To ensure the reliability of the questionnaire, it was tested using the Cronbach Alpha method, achieving a value of 0.958 from a dry run with 25 Grade 12 students at Dolores NHS, indicating high reliability. Moreover, Research Adviser and members of the Research Advisory Committee has reviewed the questionnaire evaluating its, usability, content, and readability.

Procedure

Data collection commenced after obtaining the necessary approvals from relevant authorities. Initially, a formal request for permission to conduct the research was submitted to the principal of Hilabaan National High School, Division of Eastern Samar. Once approval was granted, a letter of consent was provided to the respondents. The survey was then administered to the twelfth-grade senior high school students at the school. Following the survey, the data were tabulated, computed, analyzed, and interpreted to address the research objectives.

Data Analysis

The data were systematically organized, analyzed, and interpreted using a combination of descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, and means, were utilized to summarize and detail the data. As for the inferential statistical analysis as to determine the relationships between variables, the researchers utilized the Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r , with a significance level of 0.05).

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to established research ethics guidelines. Consent forms were distributed and collected from all participants since they were all minors. A permit was obtained from the relevant government authorities involved in the investigation due to its crucial information gathering involving children. Consent from the school principal, teachers, parents, and students were secured before the conduct of the study. All of the concerned individuals were properly oriented on the objectives and the procedures. Confidentiality of the information provided by the participants was also emphasized ensuring all data gathered are to be used solely for this research study. Furthermore, no conflict of interest aroused in the conduct of this study.

Results and Discussion

This part presents the salient findings of the study derived from the careful analyses of data obtained from the respondents. The succeeding sections present the results and discussion relative to the established research objectives and arranged topically according to research variables.

Affiliation to, use and purpose of social networking sites

Table 1. *Affiliation to social networking sites*

<i>Social Networking Sites</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Facebook	45	100
Twitter	10	22
Instagram	27	60
YouTube	35	78
Viber	2	4
Messenger	41	91
WhatsApp	6	13
Google	35	78
Gaming sites	12	27
Others: please identify tiktok_	2	4

Table 1 above shows the descriptive summary in percent of the respondents' affiliation to social networking sites. A hundred percent of the respondents are affiliated to Facebook, 91% uses messenger, 78% are affiliated to YouTube and google and 60% uses Instagram 27% uses gaming sites, 22% uses twitter and only 2% used Viber and TikTok. This result aligns with the study by Jones et al. (2021), which found that all students had Facebook accounts and most also had Twitter accounts. This supports the finding that social media platforms, including Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok, have become integral to the daily lives of adolescents.

Table 2. Frequency of use of social networking sites

<i>Frequency of use of networking sites</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Percent</i>
As need arises	15	33
Three times a week	1	2
Weekly	4	9
Daily	19	42
Twice a month	6	13
Monthly	2	4

As can be gleaned from table 2 above 42 percent of the respondents uses the social networking sites daily, while 33 percent uses the sites as the need arises. 13 percent access the SN sites twice a month and 9 percent uses SN sites on a weekly basis. These results confirm the findings of (Torres & Gonzales, 2021) stating that students use their social networking sites almost on a daily basis for personal and academic purposes.

Table 3. Purpose in accessing social networking sites

<i>Purpose in accessing social networking sites</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Connect with friends	32	71
Educational purposes (assignments, research)	32	71
Connect with family	28	62
Friends and Education	24	53
Past Time	20	44
Entertainment	8	18
All of the above	5	11
Find employment	3	7

As to purpose in accessing and using the social networking sites, table 3 above indicates the respondents responses showing 71 percent of the respondents uses the sites to connect with friends and for educational purposes, 62 uses the sites to connect with family while 53 percent uses the sites to chat friends and for education purposes.

These results also corroborate the findings of Torres and Gonzalez (2021) and Jones et al. (2021), which indicate that the majority of students use social networking sites (SNSs) primarily to connect with friends and family, as well as for personal and educational purposes.

Perceived effects of social network sites to the academic performance of students

Table 4. Perceived effects of the use of social networking sites to the academic Performance of learners

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. "Social networking sites" helps stay in touch	3.5	SA
2. "Social networking sites" enables to receive announcements	3.4	A
3. "Social networking sites" are good communication tools	3.6	SA
4. "Social networking sites" helps to get help from friends and classmates on assignments.	3.7	SA
5. "Social networking sites" helps discuss assignments and projects.	3.6	SA
6. Using social networking site improves study habits	3.3	A
7. Using Social networking sites improves interaction with classmates and teachers	3.2	A
8. Social networking sites distracts from studies	3.2	A
9. find it hard concentrating on studies using social media networking sites	3.2	A
10. Conferencing helps manage time.	3.0	A
11. An appointment can fixed with teachers	3.0	A
Grand Mean	3.3	Agree

Table 4 summarizes the perceived effects of social networking sites on academic performance, revealing that respondents strongly agree with statements 1, 3, 4, and 5, and agree with statements 2, 6 through 11. The grand mean of 3.3 indicates that, overall, respondents generally agree with all the benchmark statements, suggesting a positive perception of the effects of social networking sites on their academic performance. These results corroborate Jones et al. (2021), where most respondents reported benefiting positively from using social media.

Mean Percentile scores of the respondents

Table 5. Mean percentile scores of the respondents

General Average	f	Percent
96-above	1	2
90-95	23	51
86-89	16	36
80-85	4	9
76-79	1	2
75-below	0	0

As can be gleaned from Table 5 above, 51 percent of the respondents earned a mean percentile score of between 90-95 and 36 percent garnered a general average of between 86-89, 2 percent of the respondents earned a gen average of 96 and above and between 76-79. According to Smith and Anderson (2020) highlighted that students' transition from the activities in school to the use social media significantly affects their academic outcomes. These results however support the findings of (Torres & Gonzalez, 2021) as cited by (Jones et al., 2021) where student academic performance in terms of GPA shows a range from 2.0 to 1.50, which is equivalent to 87 to 95 percent.

Relationship between social networking sites affiliation and frequency of exposure to the academic Performance of Grade 12 students of Hilabaan NHS

Table 6. Correlation between social media affiliation and frequency of social media exposure to and Academic Performance of Grade 12 Students in Hilabaan NHS

Variables	Student's Academic Performance	
Social Media Affiliation	r	-.021
	p	.675
	N	45
Frequency of Social Media Exposure	r	-.345*
	p	.032
	N	45

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The correlation between the social media affiliation, frequency of social media use, and students' academic performance was examined using Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. According to Table 4, there is no significant correlation between social media affiliation and students' academic performance. The correlation coefficient of $r=-0.021$ suggests a very weak negative relationship between the two variables. Additionally, the p-value of 0.675 indicates that this association is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This means that the type of social media platforms students chooses to use does not have a significant impact on their academic performance.

The results indicate a significant relationship between the frequency of social media usage and students' academic performance. The analysis yielded a correlation coefficient of $r=-0.345$, which reflects a low negative correlation between the two variables. This suggests that higher frequency of social media use is associated with lower academic performance, while less frequent use is linked to better academic outcomes. The significance of this relationship is confirmed by a p-value of 0.032, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, it is evident that the frequency of social media use does impact students' performance in the classroom.

The weak correlation between social media affiliation and academic performance suggests that merely having accounts on various social networking sites does not substantially affect students' academic results. This aligns with recent research that highlights the complexity of social media's effects, emphasizing that usage patterns and purposes are more impactful than just having an account. Research by Thompson and Loughheed (2022) highlights a dual role of social media in education. On one hand, it can facilitate peer support and provide a platform for sharing academic materials. On the other hand, it can also serve as a significant distraction, leading to time mismanagement and lower academic outcomes.

The negative and significant correlation between frequent social media usage and academic outcomes highlights the potential harmful effects of excessive use. High levels of social media engagement are likely to cause distractions, decrease study time, and diminish academic concentration. In the study of Raman and Khan (2023) it was observed that excessive social media use leads to sleep deprivation, which adversely affects students' cognitive functions and academic performance. This is consistent with findings by Andrews and Arnorld (2023), who reported the digital distractions from social media result in lower academic achievement among high school students.

Conclusions

The study's findings indicate that the effect of social media on the twelfth-grade students' academic outcomes is both varied and

complex. While social media can offer valuable educational resources and opportunities, it also carries the risk of distraction and adverse effects on academic achievement. By acknowledging these diverse influences, educators and policymakers can better assist students in balancing their social media usage, thereby improving their academic success and leveraging the positive aspects of these platforms. This result suggests for further exploration on the different types of content consumed by the students and its impact on their academic performance. Furthermore, in lined with the results accumulated from the analysis of the different data of this study, it is suggested that educators must integrated social media tools that will be used for collaborative projects, discussions and sharing of educational resources. Also, teaching digital literacy that will teach students on how to use social media responsibly, evaluate information form this social media platforms critically, and how to manage their presence online. Furthermore, setting guidelines that will help the students understand when and how social media must be used that will greatly benefit their academic performance. Students must be reminded to balance their time between their use of social media and academic work by organizing workshops or seminars. As for the students, they must develop a strict personal rule about when and how much you use social media. They must also be mindful of how social media might distract them from their studies.

References

- Al-Marouf, R. S., Salloum, S. A., Hassanien, A. E., & Shaalan, K. (2021). Fear from COVID-19 and technology adoption: The impact of Google Meet during the Coronavirus pandemic. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 29(4), 665-681.
- Andrews, S. E., & Arnold, L. S. (2023). Digital distractions: Social media use and academic performance among high school students. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 38(2), 234-251.
- Bhandari, P. (2023). Correlational research | When & how to use. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/correlational-research/#:~:text=A%20correlational%20research%20design%20investigates,be%20either%20positive%20or%20negative>
- Brown, K., & Johnson, L. (2023). Social media and academic performance: A complex relationship. *Journal of Educational Research*, 45(2), 134-150.
- Campbell, M., & Wang, X. (2021). Social media, academic stress, and well-being: A study of high school students in the United States. *Youth & Society*, 53(7), 1072-1090.
- Chen, H., & Yan, Q. (2023). Social media engagement and academic performance: A study of high school students in China. *Computers & Education*, 183, 104497.
- El-Badawy, T. A., & Hashem, Y. (2021). The impact of social media on the academic performance of high school students in Egypt. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 11(2), 18-27.
- Garcia, M., Torres, P., & Nguyen, L. (2021). Social media usage during the COVID-19 pandemic performance. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(4), 3456-3474.
- Jones, A., Smith, R., & Martinez, T. (2021). Social media as an educational tool: Benefits and challenges. *Educational Technology & Society*, 24(3), 89-102.
- Kim, S., & Choi, H. (2021). Investigating the role of social media in shaping academic performance: A study of South Korean high school students. *Journal of Educational Media*, 46(4), 511-526
- Lim, M. H., & Lee, S. Y. (2023). The role of social media in shaping students' academic behaviors: A comprehensive review. *Educational Technology & Society*, 26(1), 71-89.
- McCombes, S. (2023). Descriptive research | Definition, types, methods & examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- Nguyen, T. T., & Nguyen, H. (2023). Social media use and academic performance: An examination of Vietnamese high school students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 115(3), 456-472.
- Sanches, J. (2020). The effect of social network sites on adolescents' social and academic development: Current theories and controversies. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 62(8), 1435-1445.
- Smith, J., & Anderson, M. (2020). The impact of social media on student academic performance: Evidence from a longitudinal study. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 105, 106-118.
- Thompson, R., & Loughed, E. (2022). The dual role of social media in education: Facilitator and distractor. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 19(1), 56-70.
- Torres, M. S., & Gonzalez, C. E. (2021). Social media and academic performance: The role of social interactions in high school students. *Journal of Educational Research*, 114(4), 345-357. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2021.1878634>
- Williams, K., & Patel, R. (2021). Social media in the era of COVID-19: Implications for online learning. *Education and Information*

Technologies, 26(5), 4567-4583.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Rolan B. Lactawan

Eastern Samar State University – Philippines

Santiago E. Sidro Jr.

Eastern Samar State University – Philippines

Aris A. Lapada

Eastern Samar State University – Philippines